

Fungicidal Activity: For fungicidal assay the method of Montgomery and Moore³ was used as test fungi.

The results of antifungal activity have been studied. It was observed that the presence of electronegative group at ortho and/or para position to sulphide and sulphone linkage enhances the toxicity. Nitrophenyl sulphones were found to be more active than the corresponding sulphides. Thus nitrogroup and halogen atom at ortho and para position in both the classes of compounds enhanced fungitoxicity. However, a chlorine atom at meta position decreased it. The presence of methyl group was found to decrease the fungitoxicity.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to C. S. I. R. for the award of a research fellowship to P. D. and to I. A. R. I., New Delhi, for providing the facility for testing antifungal activity.

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Volumetric Estimation of Fluorine

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Manuscript Received 21 September 1974; accepted 17 March 1975

FLUORINE is usually estimated gravimetrically as calcium fluoride or as lead chlorofluoride. The common volumetric procedures¹ involve distillation of fluorine as fluosilicic acid. The method involves complicated operations and requires time. The present method is simple and quicker.

Fluoride ion forms with beryllium a very stable fluoberyllate² ion in solution at a $pH < 8$. Barium fluoberyllate, like barium sulphate, is sparingly soluble and has a solubility³ of 1.5×10^{-3} gmequiv/litre at 25°. In the present method fluorine as fluoride ion is first converted to fluoberyllate⁴ by addition of beryllium ion in solution and then quantitatively precipitated as barium fluoberyllate and the barium estimated with EDTA. The corresponding amount of fluorine in barium fluoberyllate can be easily calculated. The method can also be used for the estimation of fluorine in rocks and materials.

Experimental

Reagents: Sodium fluoride solution standardised by calcium fluoride method.

Beryllium chloride solution	2% in water.
Barium chloride solution	5% in water.
Zinc chloride solution	0.01M
Eriochrome Black T	.1%
EDTA	0.01M

All reagents were of A. R. Grade.

Apparatus: Polythene apparatus were used when working with fluoride solution.

Procedure: Sodium fluoride solution containing 10 mg to 85 mg of fluorine was taken in a 250 ml beaker and beryllium chloride solution was added in excess. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 3–4 with *N*/100 hydrochloric acid using methyl orange as indicator. The solution was heated to 50°–60° and barium chloride solution was added drop wise with constant stirring till precipitation was complete. The precipitate was digested for an hour on a hot asbestos board. The precipitate was filtered, washed with hot water till free from chloride and finally transferred to the same beaker with a jet of water. 25 ml of 0.1M EDTA was now added to the precipitate and stirred to dissolution. 5 ml of ammonium chloride buffer was added, warmed and the excess EDTA back titrated with standard zinc chloride solution using Eriochrome black T as indicator, colour changes from pink to blue indicated end point. Results are given in Table I.

TABLE 1

Fluoride taken in mg.	Fluoride found in mg.
10.6	11.00
21.2	21.6
31.8	31.5
42.4	42.8
53.0	53.6
74.2	75.0
84.8	85.1

Procedure for Rocks and Minerals: 200 mg of the sample was taken in a platinum crucible and fused with 3–4 times its weight of sodium carbonate with a pinch of sodium peroxide. The fused mass was taken up with water in a beaker and boiled to help dissolution. filtered and in the filtrate fluorine is estimated as in the general procedure. Results are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Sample No.	Fluorine %	
	Distillation method	Present method.
D 183	0.37	0.39
D 199	0.26	0.28
D 213	0.29	0.32
F/1	0.35	0.36

Results

Acknowledgement

Author's grateful thanks are due to Dr. N. Ray, formerly Reader in Chemistry, University of Calcutta for his kind advice and guidance.

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